

Genetic analysis of growth and root traits in japonica/indica cross

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Drought tolerance is a complex trait, but the crucial plant traits that control plant water status and plant production under drought have been studied extensively. Among dehydration avoidance traits, a deep, well-developed root system appears to be beneficial as it extracts water more thoroughly from the soil (Blum et al 1999). To breed efficient root systems, information on the genetics of the trait is essential. The present study was undertaken to make a genetic analysis of root architecture of a japonica/indica cross (Moroberkan/IR20), using the parents and the F_1 , F_2 , and F_3 generations. Roots under well-watered conditions were measured 70 d after sowing (DAS). Moroberkan, the taller parent, has a longer root system, and is more tolerant of drought than IR20, which is a high-yielding, semidwarf variety with shallow root system and high osmotic adjustment capacity. One hundred F_2 plants and 200 F_3 plants, along with the parents and the F_1 , were grown in two replications in PVC pipes during 2003 kharif. Plants were screened for root characters and associated shoot traits at the peak vegetative stage. Sampling was done using the method described by Hemamalini et al (2000), with care taken to retain the roots, root hairs, and root branches. The estimates of various main effects of genes and nonallelic interaction components based on generation

means were made following the perfect-fit solution as suggested by Hayman (1958).

The results suggest the presence of epistasis and a predominantly duplicate type of gene interaction. The significant positive mid-parent heterosis observed for plant height, coupled with inbreeding depression (Table 1), suggests nonadditive gene action. The number of tillers registered significant negative heterosis coupled with negative inbreeding depression, revealing the possibility of nonadditive gene action. Nonadditive gene effects seem to control leaf length, leaf width, leaf area index, and specific leaf area (Table 2). For specific leaf area, complementary epistasis between dominant decreaseers was

recorded, showing high negative mid-parent heterosis with negative inbreeding depression. Duplicate epistasis was observed for all other shoot traits. Shoot dry weight and total growth rate registered high mid-parent heterosis and considerable inbreeding depression in the F_3 generations, revealing the importance of non-additive gene effects.

Root length, root volume, root dry weight, and total dry matter recorded highly significant mid-parent heterosis and negligible or low inbreeding depression, suggesting the importance of additive gene effects. These traits were influenced by additive gene effect. Hence, selection in segregating material can be made in the positive direction to increase

Table 1. Estimates of heterosis and inbreeding depression for different root and physiological traits in Moroberkan/IR20. Measurements made at 70 DAS under well-watered conditions.

Trait	Heterosis in F_2°	Residual heterosis in F_3	Inbreeding depression (%)	
			$F_1 - F_2$	$F_2 - F_3$
Plant height (cm)	44.36**	24.01**	-6.20**	19.11**
Tiller number	-21.80**	46.47**	-45.00**	-29.17**
Leaf length (cm)	40.08**	24.35**	-9.78*	19.13**
Leaf width (cm)	13.42**	13.42**	-6.87 ns	6.42**
Leaf area index	71.05**	146.71**	-68.08**	14.18*
Specific leaf area ($\text{cm}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$)	-41.56**	-11.14*	-52.36**	0.09 ns
Maximum root length (cm)	43.55**	37.98**	9.41**	-6.10 ns
Root number at 15-cm depth	41.76**	104.36**	-63.10**	11.61*
Root number at 30-cm depth	61.99**	72.69**	-20.90 ns	11.82 ns
Total root number	52.13**	113.26**	-64.78**	14.92**
Root volume (cm^3)	484.10**	421.81**	1.59 ns	9.22 ns
Root dry weight (g)	177.90**	159.68**	8.03 ns	-1.60 ns
Shoot dry weight (g)	194.64**	197.86**	-16.92*	13.54**
Total dry weight (g)	188.44**	183.71**	-8.07 ns	8.98 ns
Total growth rate (cm d^{-1})	43.48**	29.02**	0.37 ns	9.73**
Specific root length (cm g^{-1})	-46.16**	-15.73*	-31.26**	-19.25ns

$^{\circ}$ As percentage over mid-parent value. ns = nonsignificant.

Table 2. Gene effects (Hayman 1958) in Moroberekan/IR20 for different root and physiological traits at 70 DAS under well-watered conditions in rice.

Trait	m	d	h	l	l	χ^2	Potence ratio (h/d)	Type of epistasis
PHT	117.67**	21.45**	55.38**	64.23**	-138.24**	200.87**	2.58	Duplicate epistasis between dominant increasers
NOT	7.54**	-2.85**	-7.44**	-11.29**	5.51 ns	53.86**	2.61	Duplicate epistasis between dominant decreasers
LL	56.9**	8.56**	25.66**	27.96**	-71.6**	81.37**	3.00	Duplicate epistasis between dominant increasers
LW	1.4**	0.26**	0.18**	0.56**	-0.72**	22.86**	0.69	Duplicate epistasis between dominant increasers
LAI	4.37**	-0.2*	0.48 ns	-0.99 ns	-8.03**	11.32**	-2.40	Duplicate epistasis between dominant increasers
SLA	179.13**	33.88 ns	-40.62 ns	24.78 ns	-165*	76.23**	-1.21	Complementary epistasis between dominant decreasers
MRL	69.57**	23.7**	-6.51 ns	18.08**	41.94*	48.06**	-0.27	Duplicate epistasis between dominant decreasers
RN15	63.12**	-0.8 ns	3.26 ns	-9.73 ns	-104.2**	125.53**	-4.08	Duplicate epistasis between dominant increasers
RN30	33.49**	-0.6 ns	6.68 ns	-5.11 ns	-36.53 ns	42.7**	-11.13	Duplicate epistasis between dominant increasers
RN	108.9**	-1.65 ns	14.81 ns	-11.13 ns	-200.9**	159.15**	-8.98	Duplicate epistasis between dominant increasers
RTV	56.39**	3.99**	14.46 ns	-25.04*	-25.29 ns	13.76**	3.62	Duplicate epistasis between dominant increasers
RDW	5.11**	0.7**	-0.09 ns	-2.4 ns	1.76 ns	79.77**	-0.13	Duplicate epistasis between dominant decreasers
SDW	12.85**	0.82**	3.4 ns	-2.21 ns	-14.26**	196.2**	4.15	Duplicate epistasis between dominant increasers
TDW	18.46**	1.52**	3.49 ns	-4.62 ns	-12.49 ns	188.96**	2.30	Duplicate epistasis between dominant increasers
TGR	2.67**	0.64**	0.69**	1.17**	-1.37**	115.09**	1.08	Duplicate epistasis between dominant increasers
SRL	17.08**	3.56**	-11.5**	-	-	1.43 ns	-3.23	-
R/S	0.473**	6.99**	-0.14*	0.03 ns	0.61**	9.35**	-0.02	Duplicate epistasis between dominant decreasers
RDW/T	0.88**	0.37**	0.8**	-	-	0.578 ns	2.16	-

^a PHT = plant height

MRL = maximum

volume (cm³), RDW = root

length/growth period, SRL = specific root length (cm g⁻¹), R/S = root-shoot ratio, dry weight basis, RDW/TL = root dry weight / tillers (g). * = significant at 5%, ** = significant at 1%, ns = nonsignificant.

² g⁻¹),

the desired trait. Root number is highly influenced by dominance/dominance gene effects, making selection in early generations ineffective.

Ekanayake et al (1985) reported a preponderance of additive gene effects in controlling root length dominance effect for root volume and root number. Sun and Zhang (1995) found both additive and nonadditive gene action controlling root number. Growth-related traits were found to be under dominance × dominance gene effects, followed by additive × additive gene interactions and dominance effects. Hence, selection should be delayed to later generations to allow fixation of sufficient epistatic interaction. Root-related traits showing a preponderance of additive effects (root length, root volume, root dry weight, and total dry matter) can be improved through selection in segregating material. In the present study, duplicate

epistasis was recorded for a majority of the traits. In many of the heterotic crosses where epistasis has been investigated, duplicate epistasis rather than the complementary type has been observed (Kearsey and Pooni 1996).

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